

A Discrete-Event Simheuristic for Enhancing Urban Mobility

Mohammad Peyman^{a,*}, Xabier A. Martín^a, Javier Panadero^b, Angel A. Juan^a

^a*Research Center on Production Management and Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de València, Plaza Ferrandiz-Salvador, Alcoy, 03801, Alicante, Spain*

^b*Department of Computer Architecture & Operating Systems, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Carrer de les Sitges, Bellaterra, 08193, Barcelona, Spain*

Abstract

This paper addresses a rich variant of the team orienteering problem under uncertainty to improve urban mobility. Specifically, we conduct a case study using real-world data from urban transportation hubs in Barcelona, gathered from Open Data Barcelona. The study involves routing autonomous delivery drones operating within a university campus to deliver items to designated drop-off points. Traditional optimization techniques often fail to account for the stochastic fluctuations inherent in urban traffic and the complex interactions between various transportation activities. To address these challenges, this research employs a simheuristic framework that combines heuristic optimization with commercial simulation software to replicate the dynamic and uncertain nature of urban environments accurately. The efficiency and practical applicability of our simheuristic framework are demonstrated through comprehensive computational experiments in a real-world context.

Keywords: Team orienteering problem, Urban mobility, Simheuristics, Simulation commercial software

^{*}This work was partially funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (PRE2020-091842, PID2022-138860NB-I00, RED2022-134703-T) and the Horizon Europe program (HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-01-14-101092612).

^{*}Corresponding author

Email addresses: `mpeyman@upv.es` (Mohammad Peyman), `xmartinso@upv.es` (Xabier A. Martín), `javier.panadero@uab.cat` (Javier Panadero), `ajuanp@upv.es` (Angel A. Juan)

1. Introduction

The daily decision-making in urban transportation management involves addressing questions such as: “*How can we achieve the most effective route planning to reduce traffic congestion?*”, “*What strategies allow for the flexible adaptation of routes in response to sudden traffic changes?*”, and “*Can our current transportation infrastructure adequately handle future urban demands?*”. These questions highlight the challenges inherent in urban mobility, due to (i) the broad interpretation of “effectiveness” among varying urban objectives, (ii) the critical but often neglected factors like changing traffic conditions, and (iii) the complex relationships among all components of the urban transport system, from vehicle flow to public transit efficiency and the safety of different transport modes. To model these urban transportation management challenges, we propose a variant of the team orienteering problem (TOP). The TOP is a complex combinatorial optimization problem that focuses on maximizing the collected rewards of visited customers by a team of vehicles under several constraints [1]. This variant divides the customers into different interconnected zones, where each node in a zone shares limited resources such as charging stations, fueling points, or service docks. By allowing only one vehicle to service an interconnected node at a time, the system prevents resource contention and optimizes utilization. Specifically, only one vehicle can service a node of the interconnected zone, while the rest wanting to service other interconnected nodes will have to wait until the first vehicle finishes the service. Moreover, the time needed to service the customers is uncertain and caused by factors such as weather conditions. This can be modeled using random variables that follow probability distributions to capture the natural uncertainty in service times within an urban network. To demonstrate the practical applicability of the proposed problem, we present a real-world case study involving autonomous delivery drones operating within a university campus. This scenario reflects the challenges faced by last-mile delivery systems in controlled environments such as large campuses, or industrial complexes. The case study utilizes data from Open Data Barcelona (<https://opendata-ajuntament.barcelona.cat/>, accessed on 22 November 2024) to model the customers and distances within the campus setting. The autonomous drones navigate the campus to deliver items to designated drop-off points, facing operational constraints due to limited access points within certain campus zones. Only one robot can operate in these areas at a time to prevent congestion and ensure safety, necessitating effective routing

to maximize efficiency while adhering to these constraints. Figure 1 illustrates several urban transportation hubs and key infrastructures of the real-world case study, including electric charging stations (green), bike-sharing stations (orange), car-sharing spots (purple), public transit stops (blue), and pedestrian-oriented zones (red). This schema demonstrates the complex interplay between different modes of transportation and their spatial distribution across the urban landscape within such dynamic environments.

Figure 1: Transportation hubs and key infrastructures of the Barcelona city case study.

The unpredictable nature of real-world systems needs simulation for modeling and addressing uncertainty [2]. In particular, simulation is particularly effective for modeling complex systems with stochastic variables and analyzing their potential behavior under varying conditions. Moreover, the emergence of advanced analytical technologies and approaches marks a critical phase in urban transportation management [3]. Among these innovations, discrete-event simulation (DES) stands out as a robust methodology for addressing the complexities of urban vehicle routing. Many studies in the scientific literature employ Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) to reflect the uncertainty of real-world scenarios. However, this method falls short when modeling complex interactions between agents. DES offers a scalable and adaptable framework that significantly enhances the modeling and solution strategies, especially in more complex settings.

This paper introduces a simheuristic methodology that combines heuristic optimization with DES to solve the aforementioned problem. Specifically, it employs two optimization approaches for numerical comparison with

FlexSim, a well-established commercial simulation software, to emulate the complex and fluctuating nature of urban settings [4]. Hence, the primary contributions of this study are as follows: (i) to develop a discrete-event model that reflects the realistic dimensions of urban mobility; and (ii) to introduce an integrated heuristic-simulation approach that uses DES for solving a realistic variant of the TOP. To the best of our knowledge, the integration of DES with heuristic optimization emerges as an attractive area for future exploration, which guarantees to unlock new potentials in understanding and solving complex variants of the TOP.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a review of relevant research on the key concepts covered in this study. Section 3 introduces this realistic variant of the TOP. Section 4 describes the proposed solution approach for tackling this optimization problem. Section 5 provides the computational experiments to test the proposed methodology, as well as a discussion of the obtained results. Section 6 describes the proposed case study, its implementation using FlexSim, and the obtained results. Lastly, Section 7 reviews the main findings and recommendations for future research.

2. Literature Review

This section reviews the background concepts and recent works related to the methodology presented in this paper. First, urban mobility challenges and transport modeling theories are introduced. This is followed by recent works on TOP applications and simheuristics approaches.

2.1. Urban Mobility Challenges

Urban mobility presents complex challenges that combine transportation systems, energy consumption, and information and communication technologies (ICT). Addressing these issues is essential for developing sustainable, efficient, and equitable urban transportation networks. Cities deal with issues such as traffic congestion, limited infrastructure, and pollution caused by increasing urbanization and vehicle use. Recently, Butler et al. [5] highlighted six key areas of innovation in transportation: intelligent transport systems, alternative fuel systems, automated driving, shared mobility services, demand-responsive transport, and integrated mobility systems. These advancements aimed to improve urban mobility while reducing environmental and social impacts. Canitez et al. [6] offered a comprehensive analysis

of modern technologies in urban transportation, exploring innovations like autonomous vehicles, electric mobility, and shared transportation services, and their potential to transform urban mobility systems. It highlighted challenges such as infrastructure adaptation, regulatory gaps, data privacy concerns, and equitable access, while also emphasizing opportunities, including enhanced efficiency, reduced emissions, economic growth, and improved quality of life through smart mobility technologies. Jiang et al. [7] explored the integration of renewable energy into urban transportation systems, reviewing practices like solar-powered public transit and electric vehicle charging infrastructure while analyzing emerging trends to reduce the carbon footprint of urban mobility.

Furthermore, transportation significantly contributes to energy consumption, primarily relying on fossil fuels, which impacts environmental sustainability. In this context, Esfandi et al. [8] emphasized the need for integrating energy planning into urban mobility strategies. This includes optimizing energy use in transportation systems, enhancing the efficiency of electric vehicle infrastructure, and advancing renewable energy solutions to reduce dependence on non-renewable energy sources. Similarly, ICT plays a significant role in enhancing urban mobility by enabling smart systems that monitor and manage traffic, optimize routes, and provide real-time information to users. Recently, Paiva et al. [9] discussed the potential of ICT-enabled intelligent transportation systems, emphasizing challenges such as ensuring data security, integrating diverse technologies, and maintaining reliable communication networks.

2.2. Transport Modeling Theories

Transport modeling theories provide essential frameworks for understanding and predicting the behavior of transportation networks. They provide insight into traffic flow, travel demand, and the relationships between different components of the transportation network. These theories serve as the framework for the creation of transport system models (TSMs), which are practical tools that planners and engineers use to simulate and analyze transportation scenarios. Transport system theories (TST) encompass a range of conceptual frameworks aimed at understanding the dynamics of transportation networks. These include methods such as traffic flow theory which examines the movement of vehicles on roadways, focusing on the relationships between traffic density, speed, and flow. The TST and behavioral

approaches are fundamental in simulating user travel choices. Extensive literature exists on TST and TSM, with various studies exploring hypotheses for simulating path choices at the urban level. In this context, Tian et al. [10] provided a comprehensive review of route choice modeling in urban rail transit networks. The authors discussed the evolution of modeling approaches, including probabilistic and retrospective models, and highlighted the importance of understanding passenger behavior in path selection. Canoy et al. [11] investigated a decision support system where the routing engine learned from the subjective decisions that human planners have made in the past, rather than optimizing a distance-based objective criterion. This approach captured implicit preferences and behaviors, leading to more effective routing strategies. These studies underscore the critical role of behavioral approaches in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of transport system models, particularly in urban settings where path choice behavior is complex and influenced by multiple factors.

2.3. Team Orienteering Problems

Numerous exact methods have been proposed in the literature to solve the TOP. These methods involve branch and cut algorithms [12, 13], branch-and-price approaches [14, 15], column generation techniques [16], and branch-cut-and-price methodologies [17, 18]. While these exact methods were extensively developed and applied, they often encountered significant challenges when dealing with large-scale instances, primarily due to the substantial computational time required to achieve optimality [19]. As a result, most solution methods relied on heuristics or metaheuristics. Among these, the variable neighborhood search (VNS) algorithm stood out as a prominent trajectory metaheuristic, frequently employed to address TOP [20, 21]. Other metaheuristics similar to VNS were also utilized. For instance, Hammami et al. [22] introduced a hybrid adaptive large neighborhood search, while Souffriau et al. [23] presented a greedy randomized adaptive search procedure. Evolutionary algorithms have also been used to tackle the TOP. Dang et al. [24] introduced a particle swarm optimization algorithm inspired by the collective behavior of wild animals [25], with a similar approach proposed by Muthuswamy and Lam [26]. Additionally, genetic algorithms [27], ant colony optimization [28], and memetic algorithms [29, 30] were commonly employed evolutionary techniques in the literature.

In the stochastic TOP, various studies investigated strategies such as stochastic programming [31], robust optimization [32], and more recently,

the use of simheuristic approaches [33]. Additionally, several versions of the TOP were developed to address specific real-world scenarios. These included considerations for heterogeneous vehicle capacities, customer time constraints, and unpredictable travel times and profits. For instance, Kirac et al. [34] explored the TOP with time windows, Lin and Vincent [35] examined the TOP with mandatory visits, and Gunawan et al. [36] focused on the TOP with variable profits. As for the dynamic version of the TOP, Li et al. [37] proposed an agile optimization heuristic for solving dynamic TOP with mandatory visits, emphasizing single-source and depot scenarios. Their approach utilized real-life open data repositories to continuously re-optimize the system, adapting to real-time changes. Similarly, Panadero et al. [38] presented a method combining a biased randomized heuristic with parallel programming techniques to re-optimize the TOP in real-time based on current traffic conditions. While these studies primarily focused on dynamic travel times, other research explored dynamics in various problem variables. For instance, Le et al. [39] tackled a dynamic variant of the orienteering problem where node rewards and the maximum travel time could change during optimization.

2.4. Simheuristics

Simheuristics, which integrate simulation into optimization algorithms, are designed to manage uncertainty in complex systems effectively. This simulation-optimization technique has been applied across various domains to enhance decision-making and operational efficiency under uncertain conditions. For instance, Kumar et al. [40] proposed a simulation-optimization method to improve the quality of service in critical infrastructure systems. Specifically, they incorporated Industry 4.0 components such as Internet of Things and cyber-physical systems. Their methodology developed a geographical location-independent system using heuristic optimization techniques to identify optimized quality of service parameters, thus improving overall network performance. This approach was demonstrated through a case study on Dehradun’s bus transport system, where the feasibility of electric recharging units under different traffic conditions was analyzed via simulation. Similarly, Oliva et al. [41] introduced fuzzy simheuristics, extending traditional simheuristic algorithms with fuzzy systems to manage both stochastic and non-stochastic uncertainties in optimization problems. Their approach showcased the ability to optimize complex, large-scale problems under various uncertainty scenarios through a demonstration involving

the TOP with dual stochastic and fuzzy rewards. In another study, Peidro et al. [42] addressed the uncapacitated facility location problem under uncertainty by proposing a simheuristic algorithm that considered stochastic service costs modeled as random variables. This methodology integrated a tabu search metaheuristic and a path-relinking approach with simulation techniques to find near-optimal solutions, thus enhancing the effectiveness of traditional heuristic methods in handling real-life system unpredictability. Addressing the time-dependent waste collection problem, Gruler et al. [43] presented a simheuristic approach that incorporated MCS into a metaheuristic framework. This method accounted for time dependencies and stochastic travel speeds, improving the realism and robustness of routing solutions. The approach combined biased randomization techniques with an iterated local search algorithm, allowing for detailed statistical risk analysis and route robustness assessment. A case study using real-life data from Sabadell, Spain, demonstrated the practical applicability and effectiveness of this optimization procedure. In omnichannel retailing, Martins et al. [44] introduced a simheuristic approach to tackle the omnichannel vehicle routing problem with stochastic travel times. This methodology extended the classical vehicle routing problem to a two-echelon distribution network, integrating a multi-start procedure using a savings-based biased-randomization heuristic combined with MCS. This approach generated diverse and feasible solutions quickly while assessing the reliability of distribution plans under uncertainty, thereby improving supply chain efficiency and customer service levels. Furthermore, Tordecilla et al. [45] reviewed the application of hybrid simulation-optimization methods for designing resilient supply chain networks under uncertainty. The study emphasized the need for resilience in supply chain network design to handle disruptions such as natural disasters, human-induced events, and global crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. By integrating optimization and simulation techniques, the proposed methodology aimed to enhance the robustness and adaptability of supply chain networks, ensuring efficient long-term operations despite unpredictable disruptions. The review provided a comprehensive analysis of key quantitative approaches and identified open challenges for the simulation-optimization community, highlighting future research directions.

In the context of the increasing complexity of real-world systems, several studies use the combination of DES with optimization effectively. For instance, Rabe et al. [46] combined DES with a genetic algorithm to obtain accurate results on the stochastic performance of solutions generated by the

metaheuristic, and provide feedback to better guide the metaheuristic search. A case study, based on a typical manufacturing system, was introduced and tested using different speeding-up techniques. Leon et al. [47] introduced a DES framework for optimizing storage location assignments in supply chains, which impact their efficiency. Their approach solved the problem by integrating order sequences and picking routes into the solution construction, using simulation to mitigate the impact of random events on the solution quality. Their framework was tested under a number of computational experiments that showed its effectiveness. Similarly, Leon et al. [48] addressed a problem related to task sequencing, where the queue formation dynamics and the resource sharing dictate the scheduling. They devised a heuristic procedure to generate potential task sequences, which were evaluated within a DES model. A number of computational experiments were developed to validate the proposed method. This combination enabled the generation of high-quality realistically assessable solutions. Recently, Neroni et al. [49] introduced a simulation optimization algorithm to minimize the makespan in realistic automated storage and retrieval systems commonly found in the steel sector. This system included weight and quality constraints for the selected items. Their hybrid approach combined DES with biased-randomized heuristics, enabling efficient handling of complex time dependencies inherent in such dynamic scenarios. A series of computational experiments illustrated the potential of this approach, which surpassed an alternative method based on traditional simulated annealing.

Table 1 summarizes key studies that address urban mobility challenges, showcasing advancements in transport modeling, team orienteering problems, and simheuristic methods for complex optimization under uncertainty.

Table 1: Summary of reviewed papers.

Paper	Year	Application	Key Contributions
Butler et al. [5]	2020	Urban Mobility Challenges	Identified six key areas of innovation in transportation, including intelligent transport systems and automated driving.
Canitez et al. [6]	2020	Urban Mobility Challenges	Analyzed modern technologies like autonomous vehicles and electric mobility, exploring their potential to transform urban mobility.
Jiang et al. [7]	2024	Renewable Energy in Urban Mobility	Explored integrating renewable energy into urban transport, such as solar-powered transit and EV charging infrastructure.
Esfandi et al. [8]	2024	Energy Planning in Urban Mobility	Emphasized integrating energy planning into mobility strategies to optimize energy use and enhance EV infrastructure.
Paiva et al. [9]	2021	ICT in Urban Mobility	Discussed ICT-enabled intelligent transportation systems, highlighting challenges like data security and technology integration.
Tian et al. [10]	2024	Transport Modeling Theories	Reviewed route choice modeling in urban rail networks, emphasizing passenger behavior in path selection.
Canoy et al. [11]	2023	Transport Modeling Theories	Investigated routing engines learning from past human decisions to capture implicit preferences for better routing strategies.
Souffriau et al. [23]	2013	TOP	Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedure for multi-constraint orienteering.
Hamami et al. [22]	2019	TOP	Hybrid Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search for improved solution quality.
Panadero et al. [33]	2020	TOP	Sim-VNS framework integrating MCS with VNS for stochastic travel times.
Evers et al. [31]	2014	TOP	Two-stage stochastic programming for addressing uncertainties in the TOP.
Yu et al. [32]	2022	TOP	Robust optimization methods for handling uncertainties in the TOP.
Li et al. [37]	2022	TOP	Agile Optimization heuristic for solving dynamic TOP with mandatory visits, real-time re-optimization using open data.
Panadero et al. [38]	2021	TOP	Biased Randomized Heuristic with parallel programming to re-optimize dynamic TOP in real-time based on current traffic conditions.
Le et al. [39]	2022	TOP	Dynamic Orienteering Problem with changing node rewards and maximum travel time, heuristic based on Variable Neighborhood Search.
Rabe et al. [46]	2020	Simheuristic	General Uncertainty Management, Tackling uncertainty in optimization problems.
Kumar et al. [40]	2020	Simheuristic	Critical Infrastructure Systems, Improved quality of service in network performance.
Oliva et al. [41]	2020	Simheuristic - TOP	Fuzzy simheuristics, Handling stochastic and non-stochastic uncertainties, Optimization of TOP with dual rewards.
Peidro et al. [42]	2024	Simheuristic	Optimization under stochastic service costs, Simheuristic algorithm with tabu search and path-relinking.
Gruler et al. [43]	2020	Simheuristic	Waste collection problem, Time-dependent and stochastic travel speeds.
Martins et al. [44]	2020	Simheuristic	Omnichannel vehicle routing problem, Two-echelon distribution network optimization, Improved supply chain efficiency and customer service.
Tordecilla et al. [45]	2021	Simheuristic	Enhanced supply chain network resilience under uncertainty, Addressed disruptions like natural disasters and pandemics.
Leon et al. [47]	2023	DES	Integrated order sequence and picking routes, used simulation to mitigate random events.
Leon et al. [48]	2024	DES	Heuristic procedure for task sequences evaluated within a DES model.
Neroni et al. [49]	2024	DES	Simulation optimization algorithm to minimize makespan in AS/RS with weight and quality constraints.

3. Problem Description

This problem is inspired by a case study involving autonomous delivery drones operating in regulated areas like vast campuses, industrial complexes, and gigafactories. In particular, this scenario represents the issues that last-mile delivery systems encounter on a university campus. In modern university campuses, the demand for efficient and fast delivery of goods such as packages, food, and lab supplies is ever-increasing. Autonomous delivery drones offer a promising solution by navigating the campus to deliver items directly to designated drop-off points. However, operational constraints exist due to shared pathways or limited access points within certain zones of the campus, allowing only one robot to operate in the area at a time to prevent congestion and ensure safety. Waiting at drop-off points happens because when a robot is servicing a node within a zone, other drones aiming to service different nodes in the same zone must wait in a staging area. This is because the shared pathways or drop-off areas can allow only one robot at a time. Operational policies are implemented to avoid multiple drones converging in the same area simultaneously, which might disrupt pedestrian traffic and create safety hazards. This involves the efficient routing of autonomous delivery drones while respecting the limits imposed by shared resources and operational policies.

Figure 2 shows a schema of the described problem. A fleet of vehicles (V1, V2) departs from an origin depot, visits a subset of the nodes in the network collecting their reward, and finishes in a destination depot. The nodes of the network are divided into three different interconnected zones, where each node in a zone shares limited resources such as charging stations, fueling points, or service docks. By allowing only one vehicle to service an interconnected node at a time, the system prevents resource contention and optimizes utilization. Specifically, only one vehicle can service a node of the interconnected zone, while the rest wanting to service other interconnected nodes will have to wait until the first vehicle finishes the service. For instance, if V1 is servicing node 13 in Zone Close, V2 arriving at node 10 has to wait until V1 finishes the service in its node. This waiting time is added to the resulting route travel time. Once V1 departs from the node, V2 can service its node, which adds the service time to the vehicle route travel time as well.

Figure 2: Schema of the described problem with interconnected nodes.

4. Solving Methodology

This section describes the methodology used to solve this variant of the TOP. Specifically, a simheuristic approach is introduced that combines a heuristic optimization component with DES. For the heuristic component, two different methods have been developed: a biased-randomized multi-start framework (BR-MS) and a biased-randomized iterated local search (BR-ILS), which are implemented for numerical comparisons.

The BR-MS offers a simpler implementation, making it an effective choice for generating multiple high-quality solutions within short computational times [50]. Its simplicity and efficiency are well-suited for scenarios where rapid exploration of the solution space is required. However, BR-MS lacks the iterative refinement mechanism of more advanced approaches, which can limit its ability to further improve solutions, particularly in highly complex optimization problems. On the other hand, the BR-ILS employs an iterative process that alternates between perturbation and local search around a base solution. This approach allows it to achieve more refined solutions and strike a favorable balance between exploration and exploitation [51]. Despite these advantages, the BR-ILS is slightly more complex to implement due to the need to define its perturbation and local search mechanisms, and it requires

longer computational times when compared to the BR-MS, especially for large-scale problems or when strict stopping criteria are applied. Lastly, commercial simulation software (FlexSim) models the complexities of real-world optimization problems.

Figure 3: Description of the discrete events simheuristic framework logic.

Figure 3 depicts a schematic overview of our simheuristic framework. The process presented here begins with the algorithm receiving an input instance including details such as nodes to visit, the maximum number of vehicles, and maximum travel time. Here, the stochastic inputs are initially converted to their deterministic counterparts, where random variables are replaced by

their expected values. Next, feasible candidate solutions are generated iteratively until a stopping criterion is met using a biased-randomized meta-heuristic component (either BR-MS or BR-ILS). Biased-randomization is a technique to convert a deterministic process into a probabilistic algorithm. In other words, it introduces controlled randomness into the deterministic process, gradually shifting away from the original approach while retaining its core logic. This randomness is determined by a geometric distribution with a parameter $\beta \in (0, 1)$. A smaller value of β (closer to 0) leads to a more random selection, whereas a larger value of β (closer to 1) results in a more deterministic or greedy selection. The promising solutions for the deterministic problem generated by the optimization component are then passed to the simulation to evaluate their performance under uncertainty. Specifically, a short number of simulation runs using FlexSim are conducted to evaluate the expected reward of the promising solutions. The most promising solutions are included in a pool of elite solutions. Once the stopping criterion is met, the pool of elite solutions is further examined under uncertainty over a larger number of simulation runs to obtain a more precise evaluation of these elite solutions. Finally, from the pool of elite solutions, the algorithm returns the solution with the highest expected reward. Observe that, an efficient implementation of the communication between the biased-randomized component and the commercial simulation software is essential to provide an agile simheuristic framework. Hence, we use an efficient inter-process communication protocol known as “sockets” to allow seamless and flexible interactions [52]. This is particularly beneficial for our research since it promotes a more effective optimization-simulation cycle, which is essential for solving the described problem in short computing times.

Algorithm 1 outlines the main components of the constructive heuristic proposed by Panadero et al. [33] to generate feasible solutions for the TOP. The procedure starts generating an initial “dummy” solution that has as many routes as reachable nodes in the maximum travel time. Each route starts from the origin depot, visits one of the nodes, and ends at the destination depot. Next, the enriched savings s_{ij} associated with each pair of nodes i and j is calculated according to Equation 1 as follows:

$$s_{i,j} = \alpha(t_{1,j} + t_{i,n} - t_{i,j}) + (1 - \alpha)(u_i + u_j) \quad (1)$$

where the $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ parameter is used to balance the travel time savings and the aggregated reward. This parameter is empirically adjusted when the initial solution is generated. In particular, the appropriate value of α is

determined through a grid search tuning process, where a number of evenly spaced α values within the interval $(0, 1)$ are generated and solutions are generated using the constructive heuristic for each value. Subsequently, we select the initial solution and α value that yields the highest reward. The list of enriched savings is then sorted in descending order. Next, an iterative route-merging process begins where we merge routes based on enriched savings. At each iteration, the next savings is selected in a biased-randomized manner, and the associated routes are obtained and merged if the conditions are satisfied. This process is repeated until no more savings are in the savings list. Finally, among all the routes generated following the previous steps, the best routes equal to the number of vehicles are selected to maximize the total reward.

Algorithm 1 Savings-based constructive heuristic.

```

1: function BR-HEURISTIC(instance,  $\alpha$ ,  $\beta$ )
2:   sol  $\leftarrow$  GENDUMMY SOLUTION(instance)
3:   savingsList  $\leftarrow$  GENSAVINGS LIST(instance,  $\alpha$ )
4:   while SIZE(savingsList)  $\neq$  0 do
5:     ijEdge  $\leftarrow$  SELECTNEXT(savingsList,  $\beta$ )
6:     iRoute  $\leftarrow$  GETORIGINROUTE(ijEdge)
7:     jRoute  $\leftarrow$  GETENDROUTE(ijEdge)
8:     newRoute  $\leftarrow$  MERGEROUTES(iRoute, jRoute)
9:     isMergePossible  $\leftarrow$  CHECKMERGECONDITIONS(newRoute)
10:    if isMergePossible = true then
11:      DELETEROUTE(sol, iRoute)
12:      DELETEROUTE(sol, jRoute)
13:      ADDROUTE(sol, newRoute)
14:    end if
15:    DELETEEDGE(savingsList, ijEdge)
16:  end while
17:  SORTROUTESBYPROFIT(sol)
18:  DELETEROUTESBYPROFIT(sol, m)
19:  return sol
20: end function

```

Algorithm 2 outlines the main components of the BR-MS optimization component. The algorithm starts by generating an initial solution using the described constructive heuristic. This initial solution undergoes a short number of simulation runs to evaluate its quality under uncertainty and is set as the current best solution. Moreover, the pool of elite solutions is initialized, and updated with the initial solution. Next, candidate solutions are gener-

ated until a stopping criterion is met. At each iteration, a new candidate solution is generated using a biased-randomized version of the constructive heuristic. This allows us to generate multiple solutions following the heuristic logic, and explore diverse areas of the solution space. When a newly generated solution outperforms the current best solution, it is subjected to a short number of simulation runs to estimate its expected reward. If the new solution outperforms the best solution in terms of expected reward, it replaces the best solution and the pool of elite solutions is updated. Once the stopping criterion is met, a longer number of simulation runs is performed on the elite solutions stored in the pool, and the best solution is returned.

Algorithm 2 BR-MS Simheuristic algorithm.

```

1: function BR-MS(instance,  $\beta$ , maxTime, nShort, nLong)
2:   initSol,  $\alpha \leftarrow$  GENINITSOL(instance)
3:   SIMULATION(initSol, nShort)
4:   bestSol  $\leftarrow$  initSol
5:   eliteSols  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
6:   UPDATE(eliteSols, initSol)
7:   elapsed  $\leftarrow$  0
8:   startTime  $\leftarrow$  CURRENTTIME()
9:   while elapsed  $\leq$  maxTime do
10:    newSol  $\leftarrow$  BR-HEURISTIC(instance,  $\alpha$ ,  $\beta$ )
11:    if REWARD(newSol) > REWARD(bestSol) then
12:      SIMULATION(newSol, nShort)
13:      if EXPREWARD(newSol) > EXPREWARD(bestSol) then
14:        bestSol  $\leftarrow$  newSol
15:      end if
16:      UPDATE(eliteSols, newSol)
17:    end if
18:    elapsed  $\leftarrow$  CURRENTTIME() - startTime
19:  end while
20:  for sol  $\in$  eliteSols do
21:    SIMULATION(sol, nLong)
22:  end for
23:  SORT(eliteSols)
24:  return FIRST(eliteSols)
25: end function

```

Algorithm 3 depicts the main characteristics of the BR-ILS component. First, a feasible initial solution is generated using the constructive heuristic. Next, a local search procedure is applied to improve the solution further, which combines a 2-opt operator, a remove-based operator, and an insert-

based operator based on the local search mechanism proposed by Panadero et al. [33]. The improved initial solution is subject to a short number of simulation runs to estimate its reward under uncertainty. Next, the initial solution is assigned as the base solution and the current best solution for the BR-ILS. Moreover, the initial solution is inserted into a pool of elite solutions to examine them under uncertainty further. Next, the base solution is perturbed to generate new solutions, and a local search operator is applied to improve them until a stopping criterion is met. The perturbation phase employs a destruction and reconstruction procedure, which partially destroys routes of the solution and reconstructs them using the biased-randomized constructive heuristic. Next, the aforementioned local search is applied to improve the solution. If the new solution outperforms the base solution in terms of reward, a short number of simulation runs is carried out to evaluate its performance under uncertainty. If the new solution outperforms the base solution in terms of expected reward, it replaces the base solution. Similarly, if the solution improves on the current best solution, it is assigned as the current best solution, and the pool of elite solutions is updated. Throughout the solution search process, non-improving solutions can be accepted based on a credit mechanism [53]. Once the stopping criterion is met, a longer number of simulation runs is performed on the elite solutions stored in the pool, and the best solution is returned.

The simulation model replicates the problem instance with the same nodes, maximum number of vehicles, and maximum travel time. In other words, the simulation model replicates the problem instance to be solved in the software environment. Once the simulation procedure is called, it receives a solution to be evaluated under uncertainty, and the number of simulation replications. At each simulation replication, the constructed simulation model is launched, and vehicles travel from the origin depot toward the destination depot visiting the nodes given by the solution. However, if a vehicle has to visit a node that is interconnected with another node currently being serviced by another vehicle, the first vehicle has to wait until the second vehicle has finished serving its node. This increases the travel times of the first vehicle as it has to wait until the interconnected zone is free to service. Once the vehicles arrive at the destination depot, the solution expected travel times and collected reward are computed. Specifically, the expected travel times and collected rewards are the sum of the expected travel times and collected rewards of each route in the solution. If the expected route travel time exceeds the maximum allowed travel time, a penalty is imposed on the

Algorithm 3 BR-ILS Simheuristic algorithm.

```
1: function BR-ILS(instance,  $\beta$ , maxTime, nShort, nLong)
2:   initSol,  $\alpha \leftarrow$  GENINITSOL(instance)
3:   initSol  $\leftarrow$  LOCALSEARCH(initSol)
4:   SIMULATION(initSol, nShort)
5:   baseSol  $\leftarrow$  initSol
6:   bestSol  $\leftarrow$  initSol
7:   eliteSols  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
8:   UPDATE(eliteSols, initSol)
9:   credit  $\leftarrow$  0
10:  elapsed  $\leftarrow$  CURRENTTIME()
11:  while elapsed  $\leq$  maxTime do
12:    perturbedSol  $\leftarrow$  PERTURBATION(baseSol,  $\alpha$ ,  $\beta$ )
13:    newSol  $\leftarrow$  LOCALSEARCH(perturbedSol)
14:     $\Delta \leftarrow$  REWARD(baseSol)  $-$  REWARD(newSol)
15:    if  $\Delta < 0$  then
16:      SIMULATION(newSol, nShort)
17:       $\Delta \leftarrow$  EXPREWARD(baseSol)  $-$  EXPREWARD(newSol)
18:      if  $\Delta < 0$  then
19:        credit  $\leftarrow$   $-\Delta$ 
20:        baseSol  $\leftarrow$  newSol
21:        if EXPREWARD(newSol)  $<$  EXPREWARD(bestSol) then
22:          bestSol  $\leftarrow$  newSol
23:        end if
24:        UPDATE(eliteSols, newSol)
25:      end if
26:    end if
27:    if  $0 < \Delta \leq$  credit then
28:      credit  $\leftarrow$  0
29:      baseSol  $\leftarrow$  newSol
30:    end if
31:    elapsed  $\leftarrow$  CURRENTTIME()  $+$  startTime
32:  end while
33:  for sol  $\in$  eliteSols do
34:    SIMULATION(sol, nLong)
35:  end for
36:  SORT(eliteSols)
37:  return FIRST(eliteSols)
38: end function
```

route. This penalty results in a reduction of the collected rewards from the visited nodes proportional to the excess travel time (the difference between the actual route travel time and the maximum allowed travel time). Next, the solution expected travel times and collected reward are accumulated into variables, which are set to zero at the start of the simulation procedure. Once all simulation replications are finished, the expected travel time and collected reward of the solution are computed as the average accumulated expected travel time and collected reward of all simulation replications, respectively.

5. Computational Experiments and Results

The computational experiments were conducted on a Windows 11 operating system, utilizing an i7-1165G7 CPU 2.80GHz with 16 GB RAM. The BR-MS and BR-ILS approaches were implemented using Python 3.11, and FlexSim 2023 version 0.8 was used for the simulation model. The process of tuning the algorithm parameters was conducted on a randomly selected set of problem instances. The stopping criterion for the BR-MS and BR-ILS was set to 2500 number of iterations. Additionally, the β parameter of the geometric distribution was selected at random from the interval (0.1, 0.3). Due to a lack of publicly available instances for this particular variant of the TOP, we extended the standard instances for the deterministic TOP introduced by Chao et al. [1]. This well-known benchmark suite includes 320 instances divided into seven main groups. Each instance is labeled in the pattern px.y.z, where x is the group number, y is the number of vehicles, which varies from 2 to 4 depending on the instance, and z indicates the instance number. These instances have been widely used in previous research to assess the efficiency of algorithms in handling the deterministic TOP. In our experiments, we conducted simulation modeling and numerical experiments by randomly selecting 24 instances from two different groups. The first group, labeled p3.y.z, comprises instances with 33 nodes and involves either 2, 3, or 4 vehicles. The second group, labeled p6.y.z, includes instances with 64 nodes and also involves 2, 3, or 4 vehicles.

For the simulation modeling in FlexSim, we constructed the network of interconnected nodes reading the instances described previously and generating the resulting nodes, connections between nodes, and vehicles. To create the different interconnected zones, we determine the distance from each node to the origin depot. Following that, we group the nodes in ascending order of distance from the origin depot. Next, we divide customer

nodes into three zones based on their proximity to the origin depot: close, central, and far. The nodes within each zone are considered interconnected, allowing for a more structured approach to route planning and reproducibility of the results. Moreover, the service time for each vehicle was modeled using an exponential distribution, defined by a location parameter (γ) and a scale parameter (β). The location parameter was fixed at 0, while the scale parameter was fine-tuned to suit different benchmark network configurations.

Tables 2-3 present the computational results for the BR-MS and BR-ILS approaches, respectively. The first column identifies the problem instances, while the subsequent columns present the results under both deterministic and stochastic evaluation scenarios. The *BKS* column lists the best-known solutions (BKS) for the deterministic variant of the problem, obtained from the literature. The *OBD-R* column reports the total collected reward for the best-found solutions in the deterministic scenario. The *OBD-S-R* column indicates the collected reward when the deterministic solutions are evaluated in a stochastic environment, reflecting their performance under uncertainty. The *OBS-R* column presents the collected reward for the best-found solutions in the stochastic scenario. Finally, the *GAP%* columns compute the percentage gaps of the solutions with respect to the BKS, providing insights into the effectiveness of the best-found solutions for each scenario.

Upon examining Table 2, it can be noted that the BR-MS approach produces high-quality solutions for the deterministic version of the problem. Specifically, the *OBD-R* achieves an average gap of 9.33% relative to the BKS. Furthermore, the average gap for the *OBS-R*, at 20.98%, remains consistently closer to the ideal BKS compared to the *OBD-S-R* with an average gap of 22.31%. In other words, the best-found solutions for the deterministic scenario are suboptimal when uncertainty is introduced, as the collected reward of the *OBD-S-R* is lower than the one of the *OBS-R*. Upon examining Table 3, it can be noted that the BR-ILS approach also produces high-quality solutions for the deterministic version of the problem. However, it consistently achieves better percentage gaps than the BR-MS approach, with an average gap of 5.19% with respect to the BKS. Moreover, the average gap for the *OBS-R*, at 17.37%, remains consistently closer to the ideal BKS compared to the *OBD-S-R* with an average gap of 19.09%. Specifically, both the average gaps outperform the gaps obtained by the BR-MS approach. This demonstrates the advantage of using a simheuristic approach to effectively handle uncertainty, and the importance of simulation as a tool to evaluate promising solutions in the search for optimal solutions under uncertainty.

Table 2: Computational results for the BR-MS approach.

Instance	BKS (1)	OBD-R (2)	OBD-S-R (3)	OBS-R (4)	GAP% (1-2)	GAP% (1-3)	GAP% (1-4)
p6.2.k	1032.00	876.00	770.43	821.69	15.12	25.35	20.38
p6.2.l	1116.00	864.00	824.60	835.86	22.58	26.11	25.10
p6.2.n	1260.00	1002.00	793.71	874.30	20.48	37.01	30.61
p6.3.i	642.00	618.00	491.73	501.77	3.74	23.41	21.84
p6.3.j	828.00	816.00	654.50	654.50	1.45	20.95	20.95
p6.3.k	894.00	864.00	704.73	707.00	3.36	21.17	20.92
p6.3.m	1080.00	960.00	793.90	849.45	11.11	26.49	21.35
p6.3.n	1170.00	972.00	797.95	809.97	16.92	31.80	30.77
p6.4.n	1068.00	1020.00	804.04	804.04	4.49	24.72	24.72
p6.4.l	696.00	570.00	503.96	503.96	18.10	27.57	27.57
p6.4.k	528.00	486.00	411.65	420.14	7.95	22.04	20.43
p6.4.j	366.00	360.00	310.65	310.65	1.64	15.12	15.12
p3.2.s	800.00	800.00	695.20	700.15	0.00	13.10	12.48
p3.2.n	660.00	620.00	523.94	533.87	6.06	20.62	19.11
p3.3.t	760.00	700.00	634.33	653.10	7.89	16.54	14.07
p3.3.p	640.00	610.00	523.80	531.86	4.69	18.16	16.90
p3.3.m	520.00	440.00	395.04	403.19	15.38	24.03	22.46
p3.3.n	570.00	560.00	484.31	493.48	1.75	15.03	13.43
p3.3.s	720.00	670.00	591.31	599.09	6.94	17.87	16.79
p3.3.q	680.00	610.00	537.03	537.03	10.29	21.02	21.02
p3.3.r	710.00	710.00	598.93	598.93	0.00	15.64	15.64
p3.4.t	670.00	670.00	599.19	599.19	0.00	10.57	10.57
p3.4.s	670.00	620.00	543.42	543.42	7.46	18.89	18.89
p3.4.r	600.00	520.00	468.48	468.48	13.33	21.92	21.92
Average	789.81	705.75	602.37	614.80	9.33	22.31	20.98

Table 3: Computational results for the BR-ILS approach.

Instance	BKS (1)	OBD-R (2)	OBD-S-R (3)	OBS-R (4)	Gap% (1-2)	Gap% (1-3)	Gap% (1-4)
p6.2.k	1032.00	990.00	809.77	822.30	4.07	21.53	20.32
p6.2.l	1116.00	1050.00	857.52	881.70	5.91	23.16	20.99
p6.2.n	1260.00	1074.00	911.36	929.18	14.76	27.67	26.26
p6.3.i	642.00	636.00	505.57	508.17	0.93	21.25	20.85
p6.3.j	828.00	816.00	652.35	661.83	1.45	21.21	20.07
p6.3.k	894.00	864.00	704.20	721.36	3.36	21.23	19.31
p6.3.m	1080.00	1038.00	859.56	876.77	3.89	20.41	18.82
p6.3.n	1170.00	1080.00	884.54	902.10	7.69	24.40	22.90
p6.4.n	1068.00	1062.00	797.93	808.34	0.56	25.29	24.31
p6.4.l	969.00	648.00	528.99	539.17	33.13	45.41	44.36
p6.4.k	528.00	504.00	430.06	433.46	4.55	18.55	17.90
p6.4.j	366.00	366.00	314.26	315.75	0.00	14.14	13.73
p3.2.s	800.00	800.00	700.42	711.19	0.00	12.45	11.10
p3.2.n	660.00	620.00	542.90	557.90	6.06	17.74	15.47
p3.3.t	760.00	700.00	660.61	680.58	7.89	13.08	10.45
p3.3.p	640.00	610.00	548.08	561.12	4.69	14.36	12.32
p3.3.m	520.00	480.00	421.97	438.66	7.69	18.85	15.64
p3.3.n	570.00	570.00	505.61	507.93	0.00	11.30	10.89
p3.3.s	720.00	680.00	611.03	643.50	5.56	15.13	10.63
p3.3.q	680.00	630.00	559.17	577.03	7.35	17.77	15.14
p3.3.r	710.00	710.00	610.82	619.62	0.00	13.97	12.73
p3.4.t	670.00	670.00	609.65	625.07	0.00	9.01	6.71
p3.4.s	670.00	670.00	580.53	590.34	0.00	13.35	11.89
p3.4.r	600.00	570.00	498.02	516.04	5.00	17.00	13.99
Average	789.71	743.25	629.37	642.88	5.19	19.09	17.37

Figure 4: Boxplot comparison for the obtained results.

Figure 4 summarizes the obtained results from Tables 2-3. The horizontal and vertical axes of the boxplot represent the solutions generated by two approaches BR-MS and BR-ILS under different scenarios, and the percentage gaps with respect to the BKS, respectively. Observe that for the deterministic scenario, the BR-ILS approach achieves a significantly lower average gap percentage of 5.19% compared to 9.33% for BR-MS. This indicates that BR-ILS is more effective at producing deterministic solutions that are consistently close to the BKS. Furthermore, the variability of the performance gaps for BR-ILS in this scenario is smaller, reflecting more consistent performance across problem instances. When these solutions are evaluated in a stochastic environment (*OBD-S-R*), the performance gaps increase for both approaches. However, BR-ILS continues to outperform BR-MS, with an average gap percentage of 19.09% compared to 22.31%. As for the solutions obtained by the simheuristic framework (*OBS-R*), the BR-ILS approach again achieves a lower average gap percentage of 17.37% compared to 20.98% for BR-MS. This demonstrates the superior robustness of BR-ILS in adapting to stochastic conditions. Specifically, the BR-ILS exhibits less variability in its performance gaps across all scenarios compared to the BR-MS, and delivers more stable and reliable solutions across different problem instances.

6. Case Study: Application to Autonomous Delivery Drones in a University Campus

To model the campus environment, we used data from Open Data Barcelona, which is available in an open repository. The data contains information on station locations and distances between stations, similar to delivery point paths within a campus. A total of 34 nodes were defined, which represent delivery points such as academic buildings, dormitories, libraries, and administrative offices. These nodes were divided into three distinct zones based on their location and proximity. Thus, nodes located near the origin depot are labeled as “Zone Close”, nodes at a moderate distance from both the origin and destination depots are labeled as “Zone Medium” and, nodes situated closer to the destination depot (e.g., an off-campus distribution center) are labeled as “Zone Far”. Within each zone, nodes are interconnected due to shared pathways or restricted areas, necessitating the constraint that only one robot can service any node in the zone at a time.

The campus delivery network was modeled in FlexSim, a commercial DES software chosen for its ability to accurately model discrete events and resource constraints, capturing the complexities and stochastic nature of the system. To simulate the operation of vehicles in this environment, we modeled vehicles with a capacity of one unit, reflecting the small, precise nature of campus deliveries. In addition, vehicles traverse the campus at a maximum speed of 1 unit per time step. The service time for each node was modeled using an exponential distribution. Specifically, defined by a location parameter ($\gamma = 0$) and a scale parameter ($\beta = 0.008$). This configuration ensures that the service times are non-negative and follow a realistic variability pattern. Figure 5 shows the FlexSim simulation environment. On the left side, a detailed visual model of the system is presented. The elements represent the physical layout and flow of entities within the simulated environment. On the right side, the logic flow developed to simulate the case study is illustrated. This logic, implemented using FlexSim’s “ProcessFlow” module, defines the sequence of operations, including token generation, task assignments, and movements through queues. It specifies conditions such as traveling between queues, service time, and completing the simulation process. The visual model and the logic flow work together to replicate the behavior of the system, which enables a realistic and dynamic simulation of the defined case scenario.

Tables 4-5 present the results of the BR-MS and BR-ILS approaches

Figure 5: FlexSim environment screenshot with system model and ProcessFlow logic.

across three instances with either 2, 3, or 4 vehicles. Each table reports the results under both deterministic and stochastic scenarios, as well as the percentage gaps ($Gap\%$) between the best-found solutions for the deterministic scenario evaluated in a stochastic environment ($OBD-S-R$) and the best-found solutions for the stochastic scenario ($OBS-S-R$).

Table 4: Computational results of the case study for BR-MS approach.

Instance	OBD-D-R	OBD-S-R (1)	OBS-S-R (2)	Gap% (1-2)
BCN-2v	419.00	274.24	288.03	-5.03
BCN-3v	401.00	220.52	243.30	-10.33
BCN-4v	357.00	91.96	133.18	-44.82
Average	392.33	195.57	221.50	-20.06

If we analyze Table 4, the best solutions for the deterministic scenario obtain rewards of 419.00, 401.00, and 357.00 for the different instances. When these solutions are evaluated under stochastic conditions, the solutions are penalized as the collected rewards drop to 274.24, 220.52, and 91.96. However, the best solutions for the stochastic scenario ($OBS-S-R$) consistently achieve higher rewards of 288.03, 243.30, and 133.18 for the same instances. If we analyze Table 5, the best deterministic solutions of the BR-ILS obtain higher rewards of 442.00, 414.00, and 359.00 compared to the BR-MS approach. Under stochastic evaluation the performance of deterministic solutions ($OBD-S-R$) drops to 190.83, 164.34, and 58.61. However, the best

Table 5: Computational results of the case study for BR-ILS approach.

Instance	OBD-D-R	OBD-S-R (1)	OBS-S-R (2)	Gap% (1-2)
BCN-2v	442.00	190.83	291.57	-52.79
BCN-3v	414.00	164.34	247.81	-50.79
BCN-4v	359.00	58.61	196.16	-234.70
Average	405.00	137.93	245.18	-112.76

stochastic solutions (*OBS-S-R*) show a significant improvement, achieving rewards of 291.57, 247.81, and 196.16, respectively. This further demonstrates the importance of incorporating simulation as a tool to improve robustness and adaptability in real-world scenarios with uncertainty.

Figure 6: Boxplot comparison for the collected Reward results.

Figure 6 provides a comparative analysis of the rewards obtained by the BR-MS and BR-ILS approaches under different scenarios from Tables 4-5. The horizontal and vertical axes of the boxplot represent the solutions generated by two approaches BR-MS and BR-ILS under different scenarios, and the collected rewards, respectively. Notice that the BR-ILS approach ob-

tains higher collected rewards for the deterministic scenario, but the solutions are more penalized in a scenario under uncertainty. For the stochastic scenario, both approaches show substantial improvements in rewards compared to the *OBD-S-R*. Specifically, the BR-ILS consistently delivers higher rewards across instances in stochastic environments. This demonstrates the strength of the BR-ILS approach in addressing uncertainty and optimizing for stochastic conditions.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

This study presents a simheuristic framework for effectively addressing a variant of the TOP with the complexities of urban vehicle routing. To the best of our knowledge, previous work in the literature has focused on the deterministic TOP or stochastic variants that use MCS to reflect the uncertainty of real-world scenarios. However, the proposed simheuristic method, which combines BR-MS or BR-ILS approaches with DES has demonstrated its ability to create high-quality solutions efficiently. In particular, the BR-ILS method outperforms the BR-MS and obtains solutions with higher collected rewards under deterministic and stochastic conditions. In addition, FlexSim plays a main role by accurately emulating the complex and fluctuating nature of urban environments, providing a realistic platform for evaluating solutions. By replicating real-world conditions, FlexSim enhances the robustness of the solutions, ensuring they are both theoretically sound and practically viable. The computational results highlight the effectiveness of the solution approaches, particularly the BR-ILS, for this variant of the TOP in urban mobility contexts.

Future research needs to concentrate on improving the algorithm by using machine learning approaches, such as reinforcement learning, to anticipate traffic patterns and enhance simulation accuracy. Reinforcement learning can help the system make adaptive decisions by learning and optimizing routing algorithms based on real-time data and changing situations. This could result in more effective and efficient solutions. The framework might also be expanded to cover various variations of the TOP, such as ones using different types of vehicles or additional limitations like environmental effect considerations, increasing the methodology’s applicability and utility. Investigating the potential for real-time adaptation of routes based on real-time traffic data and other dynamic factors could make the methodology even more responsive and practical for everyday use. This would involve developing capabilities for

the methodology to adjust routes dynamically as conditions change, further improving urban mobility.

References

- [1] I.-M. Chao, B. L. Golden, E. A. Wasil, The team orienteering problem, *European journal of operational research* 88 (1996) 464–474.
- [2] A. M. Law, W. D. Kelton, W. D. Kelton, *Simulation modeling and analysis*, volume 3, Mcgraw-hill New York, 2007.
- [3] R. K. Upadhyay, S. K. Sharma, V. Kumar, Introduction to intelligent transportation system and advanced technology, in: *Intelligent Transportation System and Advanced Technology*, Springer, 2024, pp. 3–6.
- [4] S. M. Sanchez, T. W. Lucas, Exploring the world of agent-based simulations: Simple models, complex analyses, in: *Proceedings of the Winter Simulation Conference*, volume 1, IEEE, 2002, pp. 116–126.
- [5] L. Butler, T. Yigitcanlar, A. Paz, Smart urban mobility innovations: A comprehensive review and evaluation, *Ieee Access* 8 (2020) 196034–196049.
- [6] F. Canitez, P. Alpkokin, S. T. Kiremitci, Sustainable urban mobility in istanbul: Challenges and prospects, *Case studies on transport policy* 8 (2020) 1148–1157.
- [7] J. Jiang, Y. Li, Y. Li, C. Li, L. Yu, L. Li, Smart transportation systems using learning method for urban mobility and management in modern cities, *Sustainable Cities and Society* 108 (2024) 105428.
- [8] S. Esfandi, S. Tayebi, J. Byrne, J. Taminiiau, G. Giyahchi, S. A. Alavi, Smart cities and urban energy planning: an advanced review of promises and challenges, *Smart Cities* 7 (2024) 414–444.
- [9] S. Paiva, M. A. Ahad, G. Tripathi, N. Feroz, G. Casalino, Enabling technologies for urban smart mobility: Recent trends, opportunities and challenges, *Sensors* 21 (2021) 2143.
- [10] Y. Tian, W. Zhu, F. Song, Route choice modelling for an urban rail transit network: past, recent progress and future prospects, *European Transport Research Review* 16 (2024) 52.

- [11] R. Canoy, V. Bucarey, J. Mandi, T. Guns, Learn and route: learning implicit preferences for vehicle routing, *Constraints* 28 (2023) 363–396.
- [12] D.-C. Dang, R. El-Hajj, A. Moukrim, A branch-and-cut algorithm for solving the team orienteering problem, in: *International Conference on AI and OR Techniques in Constraint Programming for Combinatorial Optimization Problems*, Springer, 2013, pp. 332–339.
- [13] N. Bianchessi, R. Mansini, M. G. Speranza, A branch-and-cut algorithm for the team orienteering problem, *International Transactions in Operational Research* 25 (2018) 627–635.
- [14] S. Boussier, D. Feillet, M. Gendreau, An exact algorithm for team orienteering problems, *4or* 5 (2007) 211–230.
- [15] M. Keshtkaran, K. Ziarati, A. Bettinelli, D. Vigo, Enhanced exact solution methods for the team orienteering problem, *International Journal of Production Research* 54 (2016) 591–601.
- [16] S. E. Butt, D. M. Ryan, An optimal solution procedure for the multiple tour maximum collection problem using column generation, *Computers & Operations Research* 26 (1999) 427–441.
- [17] M. Poggi, H. Viana, E. Uchoa, The team orienteering problem: Formulations and branch-cut and price, in: *10th Workshop on Algorithmic Approaches for Transportation Modelling, Optimization, and Systems (ATMOS’10)*, Schloss Dagstuhl-Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Informatik, 2010.
- [18] A. Pessoa, R. Sadykov, E. Uchoa, F. Vanderbeck, A generic exact solver for vehicle routing and related problems, in: *International Conference on Integer Programming and Combinatorial Optimization*, Springer, 2019, pp. 354–369.
- [19] P. Vansteenwegen, A. Gunawan, Other orienteering problem variants, in: *Orienteering Problems*, Springer, 2019, pp. 95–112.
- [20] P. Vansteenwegen, W. Souffriau, G. V. Berghe, D. Van Oudheusden, Iterated local search for the team orienteering problem with time windows, *Computers & Operations Research* 36 (2009) 3281–3290.

- [21] C. Archetti, A. Hertz, M. G. Speranza, Metaheuristics for the team orienteering problem, *Journal of Heuristics* 13 (2007) 49–76.
- [22] F. Hammami, M. Rekik, L. C. Coelho, A hybrid adaptive large neighborhood search heuristic for the team orienteering problem (2019).
- [23] W. Souffriau, P. Vansteenwegen, G. Vanden Berghe, D. Van Oudheusden, The multiconstraint team orienteering problem with multiple time windows, *Transportation Science* 47 (2013) 53–63.
- [24] D.-C. Dang, R. N. Guibadj, A. Moukrim, An effective pso-inspired algorithm for the team orienteering problem, *European Journal of Operational Research* 229 (2013) 332–344.
- [25] J. Kennedy, R. Eberhart, Particle swarm optimization, in: *Neural Networks, 1995. Proceedings., IEEE International Conference on*, volume 4, 1995, pp. 1942–1948 vol.4.
- [26] S. Muthuswamy, S. S. Lam, Discrete particle swarm optimization for the team orienteering problem, *Memetic Computing* 3 (2011) 287–303.
- [27] J. Ferreira, A. Quintas, J. A. Oliveira, G. A. Pereira, L. Dias, Solving the team orienteering problem: developing a solution tool using a genetic algorithm approach, in: *Soft Computing in Industrial Applications*, Springer, 2014, pp. 365–375.
- [28] L. Ke, C. Archetti, Z. Feng, Ants can solve the team orienteering problem, *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 54 (2008) 648–665.
- [29] H. Bouly, D.-C. Dang, A. Moukrim, A memetic algorithm for the team orienteering problem, *A Quarterly Journal of Operations Research* 8 (2010) 49–70.
- [30] L. Ke, L. Zhai, J. Li, F. T. Chan, Pareto mimic algorithm: An approach to the team orienteering problem, *Omega* 61 (2016) 155–166.
- [31] L. Evers, K. Glorie, S. Van Der Ster, A. I. Barros, H. Monsuur, A two-stage approach to the orienteering problem with stochastic weights, *Computers & Operations Research* 43 (2014) 248–260.
- [32] Q. Yu, C. Cheng, N. Zhu, Robust team orienteering problem with decreasing profits, *INFORMS Journal on Computing* 34 (2022) 3215–3233.

- [33] J. Panadero, A. A. Juan, C. Bayliss, C. Currie, Maximising reward from a team of surveillance drones: a simheuristic approach to the stochastic team orienteering problem, *European Journal of Industrial Engineering* 14 (2020) 485–516.
- [34] E. Kirac, R. Gedik, F. Oztanriseven, Solving the team orienteering problem with time windows and mandatory visits using a constraint programming approach, *International Journal of Operational Research* 46 (2023) 20–42.
- [35] S.-W. Lin, F. Y. Vincent, Solving the team orienteering problem with time windows and mandatory visits by multi-start simulated annealing, *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 114 (2017) 195–205.
- [36] A. Gunawan, K. M. Ng, G. Kendall, J. Lai, An iterated local search algorithm for the team orienteering problem with variable profits, *Engineering Optimization* 50 (2018) 1148–1163.
- [37] Y. Li, M. Peyman, J. Panadero, A. A. Juan, F. Xhafa, Iot analytics and agile optimization for solving dynamic team orienteering problems with mandatory visits, *Mathematics* 10 (2022) 982.
- [38] J. Panadero, M. Ammouriova, A. A. Juan, A. Agustin, M. Nogal, C. Ser-rat, Combining parallel computing and biased randomization for solving the team orienteering problem in real-time, *Applied Sciences* 11 (2021) 12092.
- [39] H. T. Le, M. Middendorf, Y. Shi, An improvement heuristic based on variable neighborhood search for dynamic orienteering problems with changing node values and changing budgets, *SN Computer Science* 3 (2022) 326.
- [40] A. Kumar, K. Rajalakshmi, S. Jain, A. Nayyar, M. Abouhawwash, A novel heuristic simulation-optimization method for critical infrastructure in smart transportation systems, *International Journal of Communication Systems* 33 (2020) e4397.
- [41] D. Oliva, P. Copado, S. Hinojosa, J. Panadero, D. Riera, A. A. Juan, Fuzzy simheuristics: Solving optimization problems under stochastic and uncertainty scenarios, *Mathematics* 8 (2020) 2240.

- [42] D. Peidro, X. A. Martín, J. Panadero, A. A. Juan, Solving the uncapacitated facility location problem under uncertainty: a hybrid tabu search with path-relinking simheuristic approach, *Applied Intelligence* 54 (2024) 5617–5638.
- [43] A. Gruler, A. Pérez-Navarro, L. Calvet Liñan, A. A. Juan, A simheuristic algorithm for time-dependent waste collection management with stochastic travel times, *SORT: statistics and operations research transactions* 44 (2020) 0285–310.
- [44] L. d. C. Martins, C. Bayliss, P. J. Copado-Méndez, J. Panadero, A. A. Juan, A simheuristic algorithm for solving the stochastic omnichannel vehicle routing problem with pick-up and delivery, *Algorithms* 13 (2020) 237.
- [45] R. D. Tordecilla, A. A. Juan, J. R. Montoya-Torres, C. L. Quintero-Araujo, J. Panadero, Simulation-optimization methods for designing and assessing resilient supply chain networks under uncertainty scenarios: A review, *Simulation modelling practice and theory* 106 (2021) 102166.
- [46] M. Rabe, M. Deininger, A. Juan, Speeding up computational times in simheuristics combining genetic algorithms with discrete-event simulation, *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory* 103 (2020) 102089.
- [47] J. F. Leon, Y. Li, M. Peyman, L. Calvet, A. A. Juan, A discrete-event simheuristic for solving a realistic storage location assignment problem, *Mathematics* 11 (2023) 1577.
- [48] J. F. Leon, M. Peyman, X. A. Martín, A. A. Juan, Simulation of heuristics for automated guided vehicle task sequencing with resource sharing and dynamic queues, *Mathematics* 12 (2024) 271.
- [49] M. Neroni, M. Bertolini, A. A. Juan, A biased-randomized discrete event algorithm to improve the productivity of automated storage and retrieval systems in the steel industry, *Algorithms* 17 (2024) 46.
- [50] R. Martí, M. G. Resende, C. C. Ribeiro, Multi-start methods for combinatorial optimization, *European Journal of Operational Research* 226 (2013) 1–8.

- [51] H. R. Lourenço, O. C. Martin, T. Stützle, Iterated local search: Framework and applications, *Handbook of metaheuristics* (2019) 129–168.
- [52] J. F. Leon, P. Marone, M. Peyman, Y. Li, L. Calvet, M. Dehghanimohammadabadi, A. A. Juan, A tutorial on combining flexsim with python for developing discrete-event simheuristics, in: *2022 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1386–1400.
- [53] E.-G. Talbi, *Metaheuristics: from design to implementation*, volume 74, John Wiley & Sons, 2009.